

Adsorptive Removal of Contaminants of Emerging Concern from Urban Wastewater using Bivalve Shells

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Overview

- Wastewater may contain a wide variety of contaminants.
- Bivalve shells can remove contaminants from wastewater, as a refining step.
- *Corbicula fluminea* is an invasive clam species found worldwide.
- Their shells can be used to remove contaminants from the water (e.g., metals) but the efficiency to remove pharmaceuticals is scarcely known.

AIM to compare the efficiency of different shell types in removing contaminants of emerging concern (CEC) from a tertiary effluent originated from an urban wastewater treatment plant (WWTP), using a fixed-bed column adsorption approach in a large-scale experimental setup.

Methodology

shells collection

dH₂O washing | drying at 60 °C

METland® system

raw WW

* samples > chemical and ecotoxicological assessment

fixed-bed column experiment
 2 L columns | 4 L day⁻¹ | 7 days | 3 temporal replicates

Results

Shells resulted in a significant increase in pH from 6.3 (± 0.5) to 7.7 (± 0.5), as well as in inorganic carbon (IC) concentrations.

Removal of the 4 most abundant contaminants was pronounced after 7 days of operation. In average (considering all shell types), the removal was 81 % for paraxanthine, 72% for caffeine, 67% for valsartan, and 61 % for naproxen.

Removal efficiencies followed the trend: calcined clam shells (74%) > clam shells (70%) > shell mixture (66%).

Ecotoxicological evaluation (day 7)

Shells had a low effect in toxicity abatement considering responses by *Aliivibrio fischeri*, *Daphnia magna*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus* and *Lactuca sativa*.

Differences in efficacy for toxicity abatement among shell types were minor, yet significant for *Lactuca sativa* root growth.

Conclusions

Bivalve shells have potential for wastewater refinement in WWTPs.

Untreated clam shells and shell mixtures may be more economically sustainable for wastewater treatment refining due to lower processing costs plus the mild differences found in toxicity abatement promoted by different shell types.

This approach supports circular economy and exhibits ecological and environmental benefits on aquatic systems.

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